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New Indicators for Titrimetric Determination of Fluoride by Ferric Chloride

N. F. MODY, K. F. MODY and C. M. DESAI*

Chemistry Department, S. V. R. College of Engineering & Technology, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 6 August 1976, revised 3 March 1977, accepted 24 November 1977

THIOCYANATE¹, sodium salicylate² and resacetophenone oxime³ have been investigated as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride. Many other indicators like alizarin red⁴, methyl thymol blue⁵, xylenol orange⁶, Na-rhodizonate⁷, Na-purpurin-3-sulphonate⁸ have been tried for its volumetric estimation. Even 4(2-pyridylazo) resorcinol has been studied for its titrimetric determination by various workers⁹⁻¹⁰. 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso-phenols have been prepared^{11,12} in the laboratory and used as chelating agents for bivalent metal ions. This article reports the use of these compounds as indicators for the titrimetric determination of fluoride with acidic ferric chloride solution.

Experimental

A stock solution of 0.1M sodium fluoride was prepared by dissolving 2.1 g of NaF in 500 ml of distilled water. 0.05M ferric chloride solution was prepared by dissolving 6.7575 g of ferric chloride hexahydrate in 500 ml of 0.01M HCl, 1% solutions of the pure samples of 5-methoxy-2-nitroso phenol, 5-ethoxy-2-nitroso phenol and 5-propoxy-2-nitroso phenol were prepared by dissolving required quantity in 95% ethanol. These solutions are fairly stable and give yellow colour with fluoride ion and very low concentration is required for the titration.

An aliquot of sodium fluoride solution was taken in a 100 ml conical flask. About 2.0 g of NaCl was added to it. The contents were shaken thoroughly well and then equal volume of 95% ethanol was added to it, which was followed by the addition of

0.2 ml. (4 drops) of 1% indicator solution. It was then titrated against 0.05M acidic ferric chloride of pH 1.5 at room temperature. The end point is marked with a sharp change of yellow to red colour.

It was found that the presence of 50 times excess of Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ was tolerated in this estimation of the fluoride.

It is evident from the results that the fluoride can be determined satisfactorily by the use of 5-alkoxy-2-nitroso phenols as indicators, even when the fluoride content is very low. These compounds are found to be efficient indicators because they form less strong complexes with ferric(III) rather than iron fluoride complex.

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The Influence of Different Frequencies of Laser on the Microbial Production of Alcohol by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

A. S. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. DE

Department of Chemistry, University, of Allahabad, Allahabad.

Manuscript received 26 July 1976, revised 13 June 1977,

accepted 20 July 1977

THE applications of laser to study of biological system have been reviewed by many workers¹⁻³. Both stimulating^{4,5} and inhibitory⁶⁻⁸ effects of laser on living organisms particularly on enzyme systems have been found. Combined effects of laser and some chemicals on living cells have also been explored^{9,10}. But a little or no work to study the effect of laser on the fermentations has been done as yet.

* Chemistry Department, P.T.S Science College, Surat-395 001.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to improve the fermenting capacity of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*.

Experimental

The culture medium (MY 20 Agar)¹¹ for 33 culture tubes for the growth of yeast was prepared. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5 by lactic acid. About 5 ml of this medium was taken in each culture tube. The culture tubes were plugged with cotton and sterilized at 15 lb pressure for 30 minutes. After sterilization the culture tubes were kept in slanting position for a night. Then they were inoculated with fresh culture of yeast and incubated for 48 hrs at 30°. Soon after the growth of yeast was obtained, the tubes numbering 1 to 16 were irradiated by lower frequency (output at power 1 mW) of laser for 1, 5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 100, 120, 140, 180, 240, 360, 480, 600, 900 and 1800 seconds respectively. Similarly the culture tubes numbering 17 to 32 were irradiated by higher frequency (output at power 35 mW) of laser. Spectra Physics Model 125 A He—Ne Laser was used. The irradiated portion of the colony only was studied under the microscope to observe the mutation of the cells concerned as was evinced by their increasing size. These cells were isolated by pour plate technique and the isolated pure culture mutants so obtained were then used for the study of alcoholic fermentation. The remaining one out of 33 cultures was not exposed to laser and this was maintained as control.

These laser irradiated cultures are maintained in De's Culture Collection, Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad. The strain of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was borrowed from Mamfordganj distillery, Allahabad.

For alcoholic fermentation the medium was prepared by dissolving 1180.0 g market sugar, 29.7 g each of malt extract and yeast extract, 47.5 g peptone in 5 litres of distilled water. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5 by lactic acid. The volume of the medium was noted and it was divided into 99 equal parts. Each part of the medium was taken into a separate 250 ml conical flask. The total volume of the medium present in each flask was raised to 100 ml by distilled water. The flasks were sterilized at 15 lb pressure for 30 minutes and cooled to room temperature. Then all the 99 flasks were arranged into 33 sets, each comprising 3 flasks. The flasks of set no. 1 were inoculated with five drops of yeast cell suspension of *S. cerevisiae* treated with lower frequency of laser for 1 second only. Sets 2 to 16 were also inoculated each with five drops of respective yeast suspension prepared from *S. cerevisiae* exposed to lower frequency of laser for 5, 10, 20, 40, 80, 100, 120, 140, 180, 240, 360, 480, 600, 900 and 1800 seconds respectively. Similarly sets 17 to 32 were inoculated with the respective yeast suspension prepared from *S. cerevisiae* exposed to different doses of higher fre-

quency of laser. The remaining 33rd set was inoculated with yeast suspension belonging to control culture.

All the sets were then incubated at 30° for 72 hrs. After incubation alcohol produced was estimated colorimetrically¹².

Results and Discussion

The microscopic examination of yeast cells irradiated with different doses of higher frequency of laser showed that at 10 seconds exposure there was an appreciable increase in the size ($8.4 \times 4.8\mu$) and at 40 seconds exposure there was very high rate of budding. Higher doses (80 and 100 seconds), however, caused reduction in size ($4.8 \times 2.4\mu$) as compared to the parent strain ($6.0 \times 2.4\mu$). At these doses yeast cells were usually found to be oval or spherical in shape similar to the parent strain, while at other doses they were elongated. There was, in general, no effect of irradiation of lower frequency of laser on the morphology of yeast cells.

It was observed that barring a few higher doses (600, 900 and 1800 seconds) at all other doses of lower frequency of laser the amount of alcohol produced (Table 1) was found to be comparatively better than the control. The maximum increase in the yield was 36.9% in comparison to the control. The effect of higher frequency of laser (Table 2) on

TABLE I—THE INFLUENCE OF LOWER FREQUENCY (OUTPUT AT POWER 1 mW) OF LASER ON ALCOHOLIC FERMENTATION

Laser dose in Seconds	Yield of alcohol in ml/100 ml	Percentage of alcohol increase/decrease (+) (-)
Control	16.5	
1	16.7	+ 1.2
5	19.2	+16.3
10	19.5	+18.7
20	21.2	+28.4
40	21.2	+28.4
80	20.0	+21.2
100	19.0	+15.1
120	16.7	+ 1.2
140	18.0	+ 9.7
180	22.6	+36.9
240	22.0	+33.3
360	21.2	+28.4
480	18.9	+14.5
600	15.3	- 7.2
900	10.9	-33.9
1800	8.8	-46.6

the production of alcohol was very encouraging. However, its higher doses were found to be detrimental in effect. The optimum yield (more than control by 97.4%) was obtained at 10 seconds dose. The minimum value (less than the control by 81.3%) was obtained at 1800 seconds dose. The effect of different doses of laser in respect of its stimulation on alcohol formation seems to be related to the level of energy present in them.

TABLE 2—THE INFLUENCE OF HIGHER FREQUENCY
(OUTPUT AT POWER 35 mW) OF LASER
ON ALCOHOLIC FERMENTATION

Laser dose in Seconds	Yield of alcohol in ml/100 ml	Percentage of Alcohol	
		Increase/decrease (+)	(-)
Control	23.6		
1	34.6	+46.6	
5	36.6	+55.0	
10	46.6	+97.4	
20	40.0	+69.4	
40	24.6	+ 4.2	
80	21.2	-10.1	
100	18.6	-21.1	
120	18.6	-21.1	
140	13.6	-42.3	
180	10.6	-55.0	
240	8.4	-64.4	
360	7.8	-66.9	
480	7.2	-69.4	
600	7.2	-69.4	
900	5.2	-77.9	
1800	4.4	-81.8	

It was thus concluded that higher frequency of laser was found to be more effective causing an increase in the yield of alcohol by 97.4%, while lower frequency could enhance the yield only up to 36.9%.

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